

Climate Emergency and a Faith-inspired Vision and Mission for Action in *Laudate Deum*

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Abstract

Laudate Deum, the eco-exhortation of Pope Francis, is an urgent call for personal and collective transformation in the face of global crises. Even after eight years of the publication of the eco-encyclical “*Laudato Si*”, Pope Francis felt that it had not been acted upon as he had expected. Climate action is a renewed call for integral change to usher in equity and transformation in an unjust world. Herein Pope Francis dares to denounce the powers that be and to expose the mentalities behind technocratic culture. He also wants an ethical anchoring to discern and effect a turnaround, a return to roots for a more humanized technology. He points out the systemic failures in forging a multilateral action system to protect our Common Home without neglecting its least inhabitants. A certain apostolic aggressivity and incorrigible optimism still drive the Pope to take on the mantle of a Magician-Archetype whose role is “to contain and channel power for the good of all.”

Introduction

Laudate Deum, the “eco-exhortation” of Pope Francis (2023), is written from a point of disadvantage, as acknowledged by climate scientists. Pope Francis seems to have taken up the mantle of the Father of Faith, Abraham, who pleaded with God for the protection of the city of Sodom. It is breathtaking to hear how Abraham negotiated with God to spare the wicked out of His Mercy for the few righteous people (Genesis 18:16-33). After a first read, one could feel that the use of *Laudate Deum* is like the use of “*Deus Machina*” in the Greek theatre where it means “God from the

machine”, to denote the resolution of a seemingly unsolvable problem suddenly and surprisingly through a plot device (The Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2023). *Laudate Deum* heart-rendingly acknowledges the hopelessness and radicality of the situation that unless humans exercise their freedom for harmony, peace and justice for all beings, the catastrophic end of the whole world is just in the making like a ticking nuclear bomb. The God of *Laudate Deum* is not a “*Deus ex Machina*.” But Pope Francis combines the mystical preaching of Fr. Francis (Bodo, 2023) with that of the fire and hell of Francis Xavier (Rolph, 2023).

Pope Francis is not like the boy in Aesop’s fables who kept deceiving people for a joke, calling out “Wolf! Wolf!”, but got attacked by it without any help from the people who thought he had been cheating them. He is calling out a real danger to our Common Home and we are yet to see how various sections of people, namely policymakers, corporations and individuals would respond to this cry for help.

Invoking the beautiful integration of this-worldly and other-worldly spirituality exemplified in the life of Francis of Assisi, Pope Francis seems to acknowledge the way forward in these times of global crises of our ‘suffering planet.’ It is as if there is no experience of God without experiencing the beauty and divine exuberance of earthly creatures surrounding humans, making the latter’s existence liveable and enjoyable. Without humans’ organic and mysterious relationship with other creatures, there is no well-being for humans here on Earth.

Human life is bound for eternity with animals and other earthly lives, however inconsequential they may seem to be. The interconnectedness of all creatures with the divine, the importance of earthly spirituality, and the recognition of the divine in the natural world are echoed in the first paragraph of *Laudate Deum*. The *Sensus Christi* that Fr. Pedro Arrupe advocated for (Educate Magis, 2023), the *Pratitya samudpada* of Mahayana Buddhism (Encyclopaedia of Buddhism, 2024), the cosmotheandric vision of Panikkar (Panikkar, 1993), and the panentheistic attitudes of Eastern spirituality (Tabaczek, 2022), all resonate with the sentiments expressed in *Laudate Deum*. The mysticism of “the earthly heaven or heavenly earth” (Stoker, 2023) is recognized reverentially in the admiration for “all beings that accompany us along the way,” as expressed in the text.

1. Does *Laudate Deum* express how “*Laudato Si*” was not acted upon as expected by the Pope?

Eight years after the publication of the “eco-encyclical” *Laudato Si*, Pope Francis (2015) indicates his assessment and realization that “our responses have not been adequate, while the world in which we live is collapsing and may be nearing the breaking point” (*Laudate Deum* 2, ‘LD’ hereafter). He further laments that “the impact of climate change will increasingly prejudice the lives and families of many persons” (LD 2). This implies his frustration that the actions taken in response to *Laudato Si* have not been sufficient to address the apocalyptic urgency of the climate crisis. *Laudate Deum* is thus a renewed prophetic call to action, building upon the teachings of *Laudato Si* and urging all people of goodwill to take more decisive action against climate change (LD 2) before it is too late after irreparable damage is caused. Furthermore, he also conclusively points to the root cause of the crisis as the lack of humans’ recognition of ‘God’s place’ in the grand scheme of things and their postmodern mythical posturing to claim that divine place. Here Pope Francis seems to put on the mantle of a Guru or Moses in the courts of Pharaoh, who warns of the dire consequences of challenging the divine order or even opposing divine ways. The ideas in the first paragraph and the last one of the Apostolic Exhortation (LD 73) seem to be majestically connected as if in a musical slur: Creatively acknowledging divine presence, acting as responsible stewards, and praising Him incessantly requires a vision-mission perspective that humbly gives primacy to the divine order of things.

2. Global Warming: Beyond the Debate to Urgent Action

Pope Francis, quoting the Bishops of the United States, the Synod for Amazonia, and the African Bishops, has asserted how sociocultural systems or structures continue to allow the *status quo* where the most vulnerable people bear the deleterious effects of climate change (United States Conference of Catholic Bishops, 2019). The real and immediate victims of climate change are most often nature-dependent for their livelihood and sustenance and are ‘sacrificed on the altar of development’ on the pretext that there is no alternative other than the current one that reduces the vulnerable as homeless and displaced devoid of their dignity and right to self-determination.

In “*Laudate Deum*,” Pope Francis warns of the severe consequences of climate change, including a self-perpetuating cycle of global warming that disrupts the Earth’s natural rhythm (LD 5). The year 2023 saw a temperature

rise of 1.5 degrees Celsius, a scenario previously mentioned as a dire possibility, making the Pope's warnings increasingly relevant. Despite these warnings, some argue that the Earth has experienced warming and cooling cycles throughout its history. However, Pope Francis counters this by highlighting that the recent temperature rise and its impacts are unprecedented in speed and frequency, and the human-induced changes and their effects on humanity are inexplicable within this paradigm.

Scientist Hansen has warned of global warming for decades, with predictions such as temperature rise and sea-level acceleration now reality (Harvey, 2023; Krajiček, 2018). He suggests the 1.5°C limit is unattainable, as 2023 temperatures already exceeded this (Henson, 2023; McGrath et al., 2023; Saunders, 2023). Despite IPCC scientists' reluctance to accept Hansen's worst-case scenario (Harvey, 2023; Hensen, 2023), Pope Francis is not willing to explain away the effects of global warming as mere temporary events caused by local phenomena (LD 7). Coastal people of India, Japan, Africa and elsewhere need no more evidence for such an argument given their experience of Tsunamis, cyclones and other extreme weather events even while there are sceptics and deniers in every walk of life, including scientists and policymakers.

3. Climate Change: An Urgent Call for Equity, Transformation and Action in an Unjust World

Pope Francis warns against oversimplified solutions to climate change that violate human and women's rights from Malthusian and misogynist perspectives (LD 9; Winfield, 2022). He emphasizes the disproportionate contribution of the rich to global emissions (LD 9; UNEP, 2022) and the disproportionate burden borne by underdeveloped countries. Despite resistance from leaders fearing job loss, Pope Francis advocates for zero-carbon transformations (LD 10), bolstered by the IEA's report of rapid renewable energy growth (Frontline News Desk, 2024).

However, IEA Executive Director Fatih Birol acknowledges unequal distribution of clean energy infrastructure due to inadequate financial capital as the main reason why African and low-income countries in Asia and Latin America are likely to remain unable to meet the zero emission targets by 2030 (Frontline News Desk, 2024). Needless to say, this is yet again a manifestation of the unjust geopolitical and economic order that does not adequately address the fact that these countries have been

disproportionately suffering the consequences of historical emissions despite their limited contribution to the carbon footprint.

Sean Rai-Roche, a policy advisor at climate think tank E3G who has been following up on progress in clean energy, echoes the very statement of Pope Francis in the exhortation (LD 10) when he says, “Governments and businesses need to act now to protect the planet for future generations... We cannot afford to wait — action later is too late” (Frontline News Desk, 2024, para 14).

4. Denouncing the Powers that Be and Exposing Mentalities Behind Technocratic Culture

Pope Francis emphasizes the anthropogenic causes of global warming, with Green House Gases disrupting Earth’s natural rhythms and causing unprecedented temperature rise (LD 11-14). He criticizes the apathy of economic powers and their profit-driven ideology. Detailing the irreversible impact of Anthropocene global warming (Pavid, N.d.), he highlights our alteration of life-promoting processes, and victimizing creatures (LD 15-16). Beyond the tipping point, unpredictability reigns (LD 17). He calls for a collective change of mindset and responsibility, echoing the solidarity experienced during the Covid-19 pandemic, reminding us that “Everything is connected” and “No one is saved alone” (LD 19).

Pope Francis critiques the technocratic culture that promotes unlimited growth, concentrating power in a minority who manipulate Earth’s resources and pose existential risks (LD 20, LD 23). Such a minority has embarked on realizing the ideal of a super-human being using the recent technological innovations including Artificial Intelligence (AI) (LD 21). Pope Francis singles out the ideology hidden in the technocratic paradigm that drives an obsession for possessing power at any cost (LD 23). He highlights the ideological shift in modern sciences and technologies, leading to the dehumanization and commodification of nature (Kalary, 2018).

Some accuse the influence of the Cartesian method of philosophical enquiry as the primary cause of the alleged “shift in consciousness” that engendered the utilitarian modern sciences and related technologies. Are we to consider science and technology inherently problematic in the process of dehumanization and commodification of nature and eventual exploitation and abuse of the earth and humans, especially the poor and the marginalized? The unresolved issue of fixing the cause of the alienation of science and technology from the humanization process is haunting us even today. The

polarity of views regarding humans as the most valuable and entitled beings on the one hand, and the least valuable or disposable ones on the other, is a crucial aspect to be recognized in our reflections on the relationship of the cosmos and humans. The primary problem or the core problem of modernity is the creation of a paradigm where humans' concerns take the central position. Heidegger, in his critique of technocratic culture, has revealed how humans tend to consider themselves as masters and in control of everything. This illusionary belief makes them consider every being as just objects and means to be manipulated (Kalary, 2018) for fulfilling their projects or desires.

Reflections on the ill effects of technology leads Pope Francis to his incisive analysis of human power as unlimited and unrestrained in the absence of positing a power beyond it. He points to the great human tragedies in recent history such as nuclear annihilation and ethnic cleansing as the blinding effects of dehumanizing power (LD 24). He emphasizes the need for self-restraint and compassion in tandem with technological advancement to mitigate threats to humanity (LD 24).

5. Ethical Anchoring: A Return to Roots for a More Humanized Technology

Pope Francis highlights the harmonious blend of social and natural systems in indigenous cultures as a counter to technocratic perspectives (LD 27). He calls for the transformation of patriarchal cultural systems and continued dialogue between cultures/religions and science/technology. He emphasizes the need for a well-formed conscience to stimulate ethical action by those in power, cautioning against surrendering self-determination to exploitative systems. This, he suggests, leads to neglect of our duty to shepherd our Common Home.

There are many ideologies, such as utilitarianism, “the mentality of maximum gain at minimal cost” (LD 31), and meritocracy, that allow some humans to control others' lives with utter contempt for their dignity and rights. For example, it is alleged that the recent mega project, Vizhinjam Mother Port in Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, received environmental clearance from government bodies by suppressing many socio-environmental concerns raised by the affected coastal people. It is believed that in the long run, this project is likely to increase the degradation of the coast, affect the sustainability of fisheries in the region, and cause displacement of local people from their traditional cultural setting. However,

the forfeiture of their livelihood and cultural rights happened eventually as some local coastal leaders and people in Vizhinjam village started believing in the promises of Adani Ports Private Limited and cooperated with the multinational company to start the construction of the port. When coastal erosion induced by the construction of Vizhinjam Port started destroying their properties and livelihood opportunities, it was too late for them to realize the larger impact on their community's culture and livelihood.

Pope Francis raises profound questions about the meaning of life, our time on Earth, and the ultimate purpose of our work and effort (LD 33). He believes that amidst the clutter of various ideologies, it is crucial to understand one's own purpose, meaning and direction in life. This understanding serves as an 'ethical anchor' in our personal and collective activities, including major technological developments. Given the complex system of internal and external influences that human beings and their collectives navigate, it is beneficial to draw from humanity's long history. This history offers insights into attitudes that can support the sustainable and humanizing fulfillment of our various drives and desires. Pope Francis advocates for an inter-cultural and inter-religious common search for 'cosmo-theandric values' — values that integrate the divine, the cosmic and the human. These values can ensure the sustenance of this world and its almost hidden and mysterious fulfillment. However, he also warns of the potential for exploitation and manipulation by those in power, emphasizing the need for vigilance and active participation in shaping our Common Home's future.

Advanced technocratic society's post-truth leaders may dare to ask manipulating questions. These imply the myth of unlimited Earth resources: Why should the current generation of humans lower the current rate of consumption to ensure the sustainability of our Common Home? Suppose we have colonies on Mars or inter-galaxy ones as a solution to our current climate crisis, who is to blame and who is to take credit? Humanity could let the current "Common Home" fallow. Meanwhile, we could migrate to greener homes elsewhere in the Universe. What about that inter-stellar pluri-verse-oriented journey of humankind? What about collaboration with the aliens in other planets to solve the current crisis?

These limitless utopian questions may seem like far-fetched fiction even to the minds of those who do not care enough to protect our existing Common Home. But even while acknowledging the good work of space

researchers for sustainable solutions, we need to recognize those who are too eager to invest in a technocratic solution to solve the present climate crisis. They seem to give false hope to humanity as in the case of some aspects of space exploration through space technology such as Star Wars. The post-modern mythmaking continues to evade the present crisis and the need for individual and collective conversion of our lifestyle vis-a-vis our consumption patterns without caring for the future of our Common Home.

6. Systemic Failures in Forging a Multi-lateral Action System to Protect Our Common Home without Neglecting Its Least Inhabitants

Relying on the insights he expressed in his Encyclical Letter *Fratelli Tutti* (2020), Pope Francis answers the following questions in LD: 1) What is the core weakness of international politics vis-a-vis climate action? 2) What kind of a system can support strategic climate action? 3) How did the actual strategies developed in the wake of global crises, such as COVID-19 pandemic, turn out to be ineffective?

Pope Francis identifies the weakness of international politics favouring the powerful and fostering individualism (LD 34-36). He advocates for an action system protecting the commons and effective multilateral agreements. He supports world organizations with real authority to ensure the global common good. He recognizes the increasing recognition of human dignity and rights of the vulnerable (LD 39). He notes the ineffectiveness of old diplomacy in climate action and the need for a new multi-lateral approach (LD 41). He emphasizes transcending power balance issues for global mechanisms protecting humanity and our Common Home (LD 42), and a democratic process that does not preserve the rights of the powerful at the expense of the common good (LD 43).

Is a Utopian or a transformed world, in the making through the multilateral efforts to tackle climate change? Are we progressing towards an effective multi-lateral system that can ensure environmental and human justice for all, through a democratic decision-making process? He highlights the adoption of the UNFCCC by 190 countries as a pathway towards this Utopia. The signatories annually assess their performance in meeting targets at the Conference of the Parties (COP), the topmost standard-setting and executive management body.

Pope Francis clearly mentions the laudable efforts of the UNFCCC to fulfil its objectives which include:

- Reducing the greenhouse gas emissions (LD 44);
- Implementing adaptation programmes (LD 45);
- Providing aid to cover mitigation efforts of developing countries (LD 45) and
- Creating a mechanism to compensate for the loss and damage induced by the climate change caused by the developed countries (LD 46 & 51).

The UNFCCC aims to limit Earth’s warming to under 2°C, ideally 1.5°C, and is working on procedures to achieve this (LD 48). It also seeks to transform the energy sector to zero-carbon sources (LD 49). However, Pope Francis criticizes some countries for prioritizing local objectives over the common good, hindering global goals (LD 52).

7. Can People of Goodwill in All Religions Collaborate for Environmental Sustainability?

When we hear “*Laudate Deum*”, we could legitimately ask whether Pope Francis is asking people of other religious beliefs to praise his Christian God. Which image of God, a monotheist, an animist, or any other in the spectrum between them, is more conducive to an egalitarian society and cosmotheandric culture? The question is complex and involves deep philosophical and theological considerations. The complex way in which a religious belief system impacts on environment can vary due to multiple factors, including the interpretation and practice of those beliefs by its followers.

Skirbekk et al. (2020) found that less religious nations consume more and emit more, but are better prepared for disasters. In contrast, more religious nations, often facing poverty and population growth, consume less but are more vulnerable to environmental challenges. The study emphasizes the need to consider religious identity in discussions of environmental degradation and global warming. It highlights the lower energy consumption and adaptation capacity in Hindu and Muslim-majority countries, and how risk perception and climate adaptation strategies differ based on religious identity.

Religious identity-based analysis of available data on energy consumption and attitudes towards the environment indicates how the religious beliefs and practices of certain groups of people are conducive towards environmental sustainability. Though this is a complex issue with cultural underpinnings, it could be concluded that in terms of fostering an

egalitarian society and cosmotheandric culture, it is not necessarily an issue about which image of God is more conducive to sustainable practices. It is more important to ensure how the principles and teachings of these belief systems are interpreted and applied by their followers in their personal and collective lives. Both monotheistic and animistic belief systems are not watertight compartments since there have been many aspects of these belief systems co-opted in the evolution of humankind as per the needs of the times and circumstances.

After surveying the history of religions in the journey of humanity, Harari (2015:248) says,

In fact, monotheism, as it has played out in history, is a kaleidoscope of monotheist, dualist, polytheist and animist legacies, jumbling together under a single divine umbrella. The average Christian believes in the monotheist God, but also in the dualist Devil, in polytheist saints, and in animist ghosts... It's called syncretism. Syncretism might in fact, be the single great world religion.

All existing religions have the potential to promote equality, respect for diversity and a sense of interconnectedness, which are key elements of an egalitarian society and cosmotheandric culture. However, the realization of these potentials, as indicated above, greatly depends on the praxis of the individuals and communities following such religions.

8. An Urgent Need to Have a Paradigm Shift in Culture Beyond Individual Religions:

If the Western technocratic paradigm has been singled out as a culprit in the making of the manipulative and exploitative socio-cultural systems that cause the degradation of the earth, it is crucial to probe the underlying dynamics of this paradigm prevalent even today. Carl Jung has suggested the need for a deeper analysis of the human psyche to understand humans' selfish and disintegrated behaviour using the concept of shadow. Can humans understand how they have become "fossil-fuel addict" (Harari, 2019)? Does not the current technocratic system control the authority and freedom of individuals?

As Harari has pointed out (2017) a full-blown technocratic system will undermine the belief in individualism by challenging its foundational assumptions, namely:

1. Humans are individuals. They have some simple essence that cannot be divided into parts.
2. Their authentic selves are completely free.
3. Since every human is unique, everyone has their own inalienable rights.

Harari (2017) challenges the concepts of self-determination, dignity, and human rights, suggesting that organisms are algorithms and humans are 'individuals'. He argues that there is no single self, and human choices are determined by genetic and environmental processes. External algorithms could potentially understand and manipulate humans, even replacing voters and voting systems. Enabled by 21st-century technology, these algorithms could know humans better than they know themselves, shifting authority from individuals to networked algorithms.

All cultures and religions are influenced by the technocratic paradigm that leads to nature's exploitation. Human instincts for selfishness and grandiosity, considered as aspects of the Archetypal Shadow, contribute to this exploitation (Krasny, 2020). The shadow, representing the dark side of personality, is unknown to individuals, while the collective unconscious contains known archetypes (Jung, 1981). Applied to the technocratic paradigm, the "shadow" represents harmful behaviors leading to fossil fuel addiction, overconsumption, pollution, and environmental exploitation.

The Latin phrase *omne bonum a Deo, omne malum ab homine* translates to "all good from God, all evil from man" in English (MyMemory, 2022, para 1). In the context of the Latin phrase, "all good from God" could be seen as representing the ego ideal. It is the part of ourselves that we consciously identify with and present to the world. On the other hand, "all evil from man" could be seen as representing the shadow, the part of ourselves that we repress or deny, but which can influence our behaviour in ways we are not consciously aware of. Thus, the phrase encapsulates the dichotomy of the conscious ego and the unconscious shadow that is central to Jung's theory.

Robert Moore, a neo-Jungian British psychologist, made significant contributions to the understanding of the Archetypal Shadow. His work on the Archetypal Shadow involves what he calls "infantile grandiosity," which means possession by an individual archetype in its infantile form. Moore's infantile archetypes are distinguished from their mature forms where the former are selfish, and the latter, social (Krasny, 2020). The "mature" form

represents an approach that is more conducive to sustainable relationship with Nature.

Recognizing and addressing “shadow” behaviours both at the personal and collective levels, is necessary to ensure a shift in the current cultural paradigm that counters sustainable development. Critical cultural education, policy changes, and promotion of a nature-loving worldview are essential for supporting such a paradigm shift. Pope Francis’ insistence on the need for a cultural paradigm shift is getting recognized gradually:

Comparing our culture’s worldview to a scientific paradigm it is clear that the former has run into grave contradiction in the undeniable fact that the age of human progress is over, and we have entered a period of regression with runaway environmental degradation, massive wealth inequality, increasing violent conflict and authoritarianism. As in a scientific paradigm crisis, people are now wildly searching for a replacement (Back, 2023, para 1).

Walter J. Ong’s work in communication ecology offers insights into the shortcomings of the Western cultural paradigm, focusing on Rhetoric, Visualism, Persistence of the Word, and Media and the Digital World (Farrell, 2023). He critiques the Western emphasis on visual perception, arguing it limits a holistic understanding of the world and distorts truth. He traces humanity’s shift from oral to written culture, warning that over-reliance on written communication can disconnect us from each other and communal memory. While acknowledging the power of media and digital technologies, he warns of their potential to manipulate data flow and public opinion (Soukup, 2004).

Suppression of various facts of the self and society could be exposed using the application of these concepts. Communication practices of powerful states can either reveal or conceal their shadows. For example, however much fascist governments try to rely on visualism and written communication to publicize their version of the truth, the suppressed aspects come to light, captured through other media or through word of mouth of the victims. The recent tendency to portray all Muslims as terrorists or potential terrorists all over the world, is an example of the uncritical use of media and digital technologies and their impact on the creation of societal shadows through misinformation and disinformation. Another poignant example is the way the climate action agenda was put on hold due to the manipulative use of media and digital technologies for many decades by powerful lobbies.

COP 28 and Beyond

Laudate Deum proves exceptionally effective in helping us understand where we are and how we got here with regard to climate crisis. Having examined multilateral mechanisms such as UNFCCC and their functioning in addressing transnational conflicts that undermine climate action, Pope Francis clearly mentioned what he expected of COP 28 in Dubai in facilitating truly effective improvement in the implementation of international commitments. His expectations centred around the following areas:

- Revamping of the mechanism for faster transition to clean energy solutions;
- Generating a geo-political will to produce real changes in actuality; and
- Advocating for approaching the climate crisis in an integral way not just as an ecological problem but a multi-disciplinary issue.

COP 28 concluded with an agreement that aims at

- “Fast-tracking a just, orderly, and equitable energy transition;
- Fixing climate finance;
- Focusing on people, lives and livelihoods; and
- Underpinning everything with full inclusivity” (UNFCCC, 2023, para 1).

The ‘2030 Climate Solutions: an Implementation Roadmap’, compiled by the High-Level Champions, the Marrakech Partnership and other partners set forth an ambitious and comprehensive action plan “to halve global emissions, address adaptation gaps and increase the resilience of four billion people from vulnerable groups and communities to climate risks by 2030” (UNFCCC, 2023, para 1).

Though substantial progress has been made towards the goals set by Pope Francis, there were also areas where the conference fell short, indicating that there is still much work to be done in the fight against climate change. There is a mixed reaction to the outcomes of COP 28 as regards Pope Francis’ expectation of it to come up with “binding forms of energy transition that meet three conditions: that they be efficient, obligatory and readily monitored” (LD 59). The first and third conditions can be tested only in the implementation and monitoring stage of the voluminous agreements. But the second condition could not be fulfilled adequately, namely

“establishing global and effective rules” (LD 42) binding on all partner countries. Many countries walked away from the discussions due to the dilution of the primary agenda of “phasing out” of fossil fuels.

Conclusion: Who Will Guarantee Earth’s Future?

“Apostolic aggressivity”, a term that was popularized among the Jesuits by Pedro Arrupe, characterizes Pope Francis’s spirit in his approach to climate action. Never before has humanity been so acutely aware of the ecological impact of its interventions on Earth, both for survival and for flourishing. There are no nations left without the knowledge of the urgency of action required of them. With every challenge, comes an opportunity. Despite the gravity of the current climate emergency, we now have various scientific tools to understand the anthropogenic factors that have contributed to this crisis. The solution to the crisis demands more than just technological adaptation. It requires a shift from the Western cultural paradigm, which is currently being blindly followed by almost every country. Such a paradigm does not adequately address the issue of shadows at personal and collective levels.

In the post-truth society, media and digital technologies could be used to perpetuate societal shadows using misinformation-disinformation-manipulation campaign by the powers that be, even in democratic countries, to hold on to power, threatening even the very survival of humanity and our planet. “The primary role of the magician archetype”, here represented by Pope Francis, “is to contain and channel power for the good of all” (Jeffrey, 2024a, para 1). Those who remain aware of their own personal and collective shadows will expose the hidden nature of the powers that be. They will be part of the global movement for environmental and human justice. They will live their life acknowledging the limited nature of earthly resources. They will recognize the limitations of technocratic solutions to the current global climate crisis and own up their collective responsibility.

They will remain vigilant in their personal and collective efforts to protect their Common Home. They will be “salt of the earth” (Mat 5:13); salt being “the symbol for Sapientia” in both ecclesiastical and alchemical usage (Jung, 1981, p. 328). They will sing a requiem to Mother Earth, not to usher in ecocide, but to transform the current crisis and transcend the inevitable catastrophe. They will join conscientization movements with both global and local implications for all forces that threaten the survival and well-being of the Earth and its most vulnerable inhabitants. They will use a carbon

footprint calculator to reduce their carbon footprint based on their current lifestyle. They will learn more about the impact of their actions on our environment vis-à-vis climate change (ClimateHero, n.d.) and take actions to influence a more environmentally friendly and climate positive attitude in society as a whole (ClimateHero, n.d., para 1).

Before taking a climate pledge, they will join the dirge of Kurup (n.d.), a renowned eco-poet whose words will echo, down the centuries of human existence:

Mother Earth, still fighting to be alive,
Let me sing a requiem for you,
As you face an imminent death.
This song is for you -- and for me,
One that I score in my heart today.
In the shadow of the blooming, dark, poisonous flower of death,
Tomorrow, when you remain frozen,
No one will be here, not even I,
To shed a tear on your lifeless face,
To quench your thirst and lament over you.
So, let me scribble this for you,
Who are still undying, yet facing imminent death,
Let me sing the last song to let you rest in peace”.

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